

1 **Valorization of food waste into renewable fuels via anaerobic digestion and inline CO₂ reforming**
2 **over Ni-based catalysts**

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13 **Supplementary material**

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15 **Anaerobic digestion of food waste for biogas production**

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17 **Table S1:** Properties (typical values) of the food waste and inoculum used.

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	Food waste	Inoculum
pH	5.01	7.7
Moisture content (MC) (wt. %)	83.94	93.08
Total solids (TS) (wt.%)	16.06	6.92
Volatile solids (VS) (wt.%)	15.23	4.96
Ashes (wt.%)	0.83	1.96

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25 **Table S2:**Average values of biogas production.

	L/kg FW-Raw/day	L/kg FW-TS/day	L/kg FW-VS/day
Biogas production	104	647	680

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28 **Characterization of sorbent**

29 The sorbent material (Ferrum Scon) used to remove H₂S from the raw biogas was purchased from
 30 Schaumann BioEnergy Consult GmbH, Germany. The results of XRD and XRF analyses of the fresh
 31 and spent sorbent are given as follows:

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 33 **Fig. S1.** XRD analysis of the Phase composition fresh (left) and spent (right) sorbent

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 35 **Table S3.** Phase composition fresh and spent sorbent (as determined by XRD).

Ferrum Scon	Phase / chemical composition / COD card
Fresh	Calcite / CaCO ₃ / 01-086-2340
	Gypsum / CaSO ₄ ·2H ₂ O / 01-076-5973
	Anhydrite / CaSO ₄ / 01-086-2270
	Bassanite / CaSO ₄ ·0.67H ₂ O / 00-036-0617
	Iron oxide hydroxide / FeO(OH) / 01-075-1594
	Akaganeite, syn / Fe ⁺³ O(OH) / 00-013-0157
Spent	Calcite / CaCO ₃ / 01-086-2340
	Gypsum / CaSO ₄ ·2H ₂ O / 01-076-5973
	Anhydrite / CaSO ₄ / 01-086-2270
	Iron oxide hydroxide / FeO(OH) / 01-075-1594
	Akaganeite, syn / Fe ⁺³ O(OH) / 00-013-0157
	Sulphur / S / 00-008-0247

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Table S4. Major elements present in the fresh and spent sorbent (as determined by XRF).

	Amount (wt. %)				
	Fe	Ca	S	Si	Mn
Fresh Sorbent	33.83	27.54	6.15	3.03	0.59
Spent sorbent	20.66	16.84	29.32	2.37	0.33

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39 **Catalyst syntheses**40 *10Ni-0.5Cu(or Rh)-MgAl₂O₄*

41 In a typical synthesis, 2.0 M nitrate solution of $M^{2+}/M^{3+} = 80/20$ (atomic ratio, where $M^{2+} = \text{Mg, Ni, Cu}$
 42 and $M^{3+} = \text{Al, Rh}$) was added dropwise into a beaker containing 1.0 M Na_2CO_3 solution maintained at
 43 60 °C under stirring. The precipitation occurred at a constant pH of 10, controlled by dropwise addition
 44 of 3.0 M NaOH solution. The resulting slurry was aged at 60 °C for 1 h. The obtained precipitates were
 45 filtered and washed thoroughly with hot (60 °C) deionized water. After drying the solid phase at 70 °C
 46 for 24 h, the sample was then crushed into fine powder and then calcined at 900 °C for 6 h using a
 47 heating rate of 10 °C/min.

48 *10Ni- Ce_{0.5}Zr_{0.5}O₂*

49 Pechini polymerization + Incipient Wetness Impregnation (IWI) method. In the first step of the synthesis
 50 procedure, the support material comprising Ce and Zr oxides was synthesized. For this purpose, aqueous
 51 solution of metallic precursors $\text{Ce}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ and $\text{Zr}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ was prepared to obtain a 0.22 M solution. Citric
 52 acid was then added to the solution keeping the metallic precursor to citric acid ratio of 1:1.1 and
 53 maintaining the temperature of the solution at 60 °C. Afterwards, ethylene glycol was added to the
 54 solution keeping the ethylene glycol to citric acid ratio of 4:1. The aqueous phase was then evaporated
 55 to obtain a brownish resin that was dried overnight at 100 °C. The resin was then grinded and calcined
 56 at 450 °C using a temperature ramp of 10 °C/min and a dwell time of for 3 h; the resulting powder was
 57 further calcined at 900 °C for 5 hours with a heating rate of 2 °C/min.

58 In the second step Ni was added to the support system by incipient wetness impregnation method. The
 59 procedure can be summarized as follows: (i) the support was precisely weighed; (ii) aqueous solution

60 containing the active phase precursor (i.e., $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$) was prepared considering the volume needed to fill
61 all the pore volume of the support; (iii) the solution was slowly dropped on the support powder to
62 impregnate homogeneously all the pores; (iv) the solid was dried at 110 °C overnight; and then (v)
63 calcined at 500 °C (2 °C/min) for 5 hours). Since the support materials prepared are characterized by a
64 particularly low pore volume, the step (ii) was performed with a water volume three times higher than
65 the theoretical, and, hence, the step (iii) and (iv) were carried out three times rather than only one to
66 disperse the active phase more precisely on the support.

67 *10Ni-MgAl-silicate*

68 The 10Ni-MgAl-silicate catalyst was prepared by means of a modified co-precipitation technique for
69 the synthesis of a layered double hydroxide, the main difference being the incorporation of silicates as
70 interlayer anions in place of carbonates. The synthesis was adapted from the literature in order to achieve
71 a 10 wt. % loading of Ni in the final mixed oxide, as well as the desired atomic ratio between divalent
72 and trivalent cations [e.g., $(\text{Mg} + \text{Ni})/(\text{Al}) = 2$] and between silicates and trivalent cations (e.g., SiO_3^{2-}
73 $/\text{Al}^{3+} = 0.6$, equal to 20 % excess in respect to stoichiometric value in LDH). The resulting Mg/Ni molar
74 ratio was 5.5.

75 Briefly, 19.66 g of $\text{Mg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Acros Organics, 98 %), 4.01 g of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Alfa Aesar, 98
76 %) and 17.53 g of $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (VWR Chemicals, 98 %) were dissolved in 810 mL of deionized
77 water to obtain a $[\text{Mg} + \text{Ni} + \text{Al}] = 0.2$ mol/L solution, which was transferred into a separating funnel.
78 Then, 6.11 g of sodium silicate solution (Sigma Aldrich NaOH = 10.6 wt. %, $\text{SiO}_2 = 26.5$ wt. %) were
79 diluted with deionized water up to 45 mL to obtain a $[\text{Si}] = 0.6$ mol/L solution, which was heated up to
80 60 °C and adjusted to the pH value of 10.5 by addition of concentrated HNO_3 . Then, the co-precipitation
81 was carried out at constant pH and temperature by slow, dropwise addition of the nitrate solution to the
82 silicates solution under vigorous stirring; the pH was kept constant by addition of $[\text{NaOH}] = 3$ mol/L.
83 At the end of the addition the resulting suspension was aged for 1 h at 60 °C, filtered over a Buchner
84 funnel and washed with deionized water until neutral pH. The wet cake was finally dried overnight at
85 110 °C and calcined at 900 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min for 12 hours.

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88 *10Ni-Silicalite-1*

89 For the synthesis of 10Ni-Silicalite-1 sample, wetness impregnation method was employed. For the
90 synthesis, 3.32 g of Ni (NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Penta Chemical, Czech Republic) was dissolved in 100 mL
91 deionized water. In order to enhance the dispersion, 1 mL of ethanol was added to the nickel nitrate
92 solution. 6 g of MFI zeolite of the type silicalite-1 was added to the solution under constant stirring. The
93 mixture was then stirred for one hour with the help of a magnetic stirrer. Afterwards, the solution was
94 heated to 90 °C and the liquid phase was evaporated. The solid phase left was calcined in a muffle oven
95 at 500 °C using a temperature ramp of 8 °C/min and a dwell time of 3 h.

96 *10Ni-Al₂O₃*

97 10Ni-Al₂O₃ sample was synthesized by precipitation method. For the preparation, 2.5 g of Ni
98 (NO₃)₂·6H₂O (Penta Chemical, Czech Republic) was dissolved in 50 mL of deionized water at 60 °C
99 under constant stirring. In a separate beaker, 5 g of γ-Al₂O₃ was mixed with 50 mL of deionized water
100 at 50 °C under stirring and the resulting suspension was added to the primary solution. For the
101 precipitation step, aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide was prepared by dissolving 0.69 g of granular
102 NaOH in 50 mL deionized and the solution obtained was added to previously mixed solution. The
103 precipitates obtained were stirred and aged for 1.5 h, filtered and washed in a Buchner funnel. The filter
104 cake was dried overnight at 60 °C. Finally, the sample was calcined at 500 °C using a temperature ramp
105 of 3 °C/min and a dwell time of 3 hours.

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107 **Catalyst characterization**

108 *XRD analysis of fresh catalyst*

109 **Fig. S2.** XRD diffractograms of ceria, $\text{Ce}_{0.75}\text{Zr}_{0.25}\text{O}_2$, and $\text{Ce}_{0.5}\text{Zr}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ synthesized by Pechini
110 polymerization and calcined at 900 °C.
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Fig. S3. TEM micrographs showing different type of carbon over catalysts after reaction. a) 10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl₂O₄; b) 10Ni-0.5Cu-MgAl₂O₄; c) 10Ni-MgAl-Silicate; d) 10Ni-Al₂O₃.

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Fig. S4. STEM-HAADF images and EDS compositional analyses of different nanoparticles for 10Ni-0.5Cu-MgAl₂O₄ catalyst after reaction.

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Fig. S5. STEM-HAADF images and EDS compositional analyses of different nanoparticles for 10Ni-0.5Rh-MgAl₂O₄ catalyst after reaction.